

Synthesis, characterization, DNA binding, cleavage and antibacterial studies of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 3-(2-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)hydrazinyl)quinoxalin-(1*H*)-one

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Abstract : A series of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of tridentate Schiff base ligand (L), 3-(2-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)hydrazinyl)quinoxalin-2(1*H*)-one (VHQO) have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, IR, UV-Vis, EPR, PXRD, SEM, TGA-DTA, mass, molar conductance and magnetic studies. The ligand (L) formed 1 : 2 complexes (ML₂) with all the metal ions (M) and the complexes were found to be monomeric with an octahedral geometry. The ligand and its complexes were screened for their antibacterial activity against Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis* and Gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The binding abilities of the ligand and its complexes with Calf Thymus (CT-DNA) were investigated by absorption spectroscopy and the intrinsic binding constant (K_b) values were calculated. The results indicated an intercalation mode of binding. The ability of the ligand and its metal complexes to cleave super coiled pBR 322 DNA have been studied using agarose gel electrophoresis and found them to cleave the super coiled DNA into nicked circular form.

Keywords : Schiff base, metal complexes, TGA, SEM, PXRD, octahedral geometry, DNA and antibacterial studies.

Introduction

Quinoxaline belongs to an important class of heterocycles known as diazaphthalenes. The quinoxaline moiety is recognized in antibiotics such as streptomycin, echinomycin^{1,2} and growth promoter carbodox^{3,4}. The derivatives of quinoxaline have received great attention due to their promising biological applications as antibacterial, antifungal^{5,6}, antitumor^{7,8}, anti-inflammatory⁹, antitrypanosomal^{10,11}, antituberculosis¹², antidiabetic¹³ and antidepressant activities^{14,15}. Quinoxaline derivatives are also used in electroluminescent devices¹⁶, dyes¹⁷, chemo sensors¹⁸, corrosion inhibition¹⁹ and in catalysis^{20,21}. In recent years, the DNA binding and cleavage studies of transition metal complexes of quinoxalines derivatives have gained much attention²². The Schiff base ligands derived from 3-hydrazinyl-

quinoxalin-2(1*H*)-one and carbonyl compounds have not been much investigated in terms of their metal complex formation and biological activities. In the present communication, we report the synthesis and characterization of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of the Schiff base ligand (L), 3-(2-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)hydrazinyl)quinoxalin-2(1*H*)-one (VHQO). The *in vitro* antibacterial activities, DNA binding and cleavage studies of the ligand and its metal complexes are also presented.

Results and discussion

Physicochemical studies :

The ligand is yellow solid and all the metal complexes are colored solids. The complexes are non-hygroscopic, stable in air, insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in DMF and DMSO. Their

low molar conductance values ($3.4\text{--}4.8 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) in DMSO ($10^{-3} M$) indicate them to be non-electrolytes²³. The elemental analysis data reveal 1 : 2 (ML_2) composition in all the complexes. The characteristic peak of $\nu(\text{CH}=\text{N})$ at 1614cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum of the ligand appears at lower wave numbers by $9\text{--}21 \text{cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes, suggesting the involvement of azomethine nitrogen in coordination²⁴. The band observed at 3581cm^{-1} in the ligand attributed to $\nu(\text{OH})$ stretching frequency is absent in the complexes indicating the coordination of oxygen of -OH group by deprotonation. This is further supported by the positive shift of the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ peak at 1344cm^{-1} in the ligand by $13\text{--}21 \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes²⁵, may be due to the drift in electron density from oxygen to metal ion resulting in greater ionic character of $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ bond²⁶. The intense sharp band at 1678cm^{-1} in the ligand assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ shifts to 1647cm^{-1} in Cu^{II} complex, indicating a decrease in the stretching force constant of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ as a consequence of coordination through the carbonyl oxygen atom of the ligand. The shifts in $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ are not significant in Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes precluding the involvement of carbonyl oxygen in coordination in these complexes. The medium intensity peak at 1465cm^{-1} in the ligand assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})_{\text{ring}}$ experiences a negative shift in Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes suggesting the participation of ring nitrogen in coordination with these metal ions. Appearance of medium intensity bands in the low frequency region of the spectra of complexes reveals the presence of M-O and M-N bonds. From the IR spectral data it can be known that VHQO behaves as monobasic tridentate ligand and acts as N,N,O donor in Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes coordinating through ring nitrogen, azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen and behaves as O,N,O donor in Cu^{II} complex coordinating through carbonyl oxygen, azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen. Electronic absorption spectra of the ligand exhibits strong peaks at 266 and 276 nm corresponding to $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transitions. The peaks at 358, 377 and 397 nm of the ligand correspond to $n\text{-}\pi^*$ transitions. Electronic spectrum of Co^{II} complex shows an absorption band at 485 nm assignable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, character-

istic of the octahedral Co^{II} complex²³. A shoulder observed at 412–459 nm is assigned to ligand to metal charge transfer²⁷. The band at 468 nm in the Ni^{II} complex is in accordance with the ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transition for six coordinated octahedral Ni^{II} complex²⁸. Cu^{II} complex shows a band at 482 nm corresponding to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_{1g}$ transition indicating distorted octahedral geometry²⁴. Zn^{II} complex has d^{10} electronic configuration, exhibits only intra ligand transitions and is diamagnetic. The TGA results reveal that the complexes are thermally stable up to 300°C and absence of endotherms in DTA exclude the presence of lattice as well as coordinated water in all the complexes. The Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes decompose in single stage. The exotherms at 300°C and 362°C of Cu^{II} complex and at 313°C , 469°C and 534°C of Zn^{II} complex represent the decomposition of the complexes involving phase transition and or oxidation²⁹. The presence of sharp peaks in PXRD suggests the crystalline nature of the ligand and its metal complexes. The SEM micrograph of VHQO differs significantly from its complexes (Fig. 1). The ligand shows irregular rod like structure. The Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes show cauliflower like morphology, while Cu^{II} complex shows agglomerated morphology³⁰. EPR spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex recorded in solid state at room temperature (Fig. 2) appears to be isotropic indicating significant exchange coupling interactions resulting in the broadening of EPR line³¹. The spectral parameters of the complexes, $g_{\parallel} (2.156) > g_{\perp} (2.095) > 2.0023$ indicate that the unpaired electron in the ground state of Cu^{II} is predominantly in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital suggesting tetragonal elongated geometry for the complex. The value of $g_{\parallel} (< 2.3)$ is characteristic of covalent environment in M-L bond³². To measure the exchange interaction between the metal centers, the axial symmetry parameter G is calculated by using the equation, $G = g_{\parallel} - 2.0023/g_{\perp} - 2.0023$ and found to be 1.56 which indicates that VHQO is a strong field ligand and considerable exchange interaction in the solid complex is possible^{33,34}, as G value is < 4 . The μ value (1.82 B.M.) determined is also in agreement with the paramagnetic nature of the Cu^{II} complex.

Fig. 1. SEM images of VHQO and its metal complexes.

Fig. 2. EPR spectrum of Cu^{II} complex.

Based on the spectral and analytical data, the structures for the complexes are given in Figs. 3 and 4.

Antibacterial studies :

The ligand and its Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes were effective against *Staphylococcus aureus* with a zone of inhibition of 12 mm, 13 mm and 12 mm respectively. The ligand and its Cu^{II} complex were effective against *Bacillus subtilis* with a zone of inhibition 11 mm and 13 mm respectively. The variable antibacterial activity has been associated with the nature of the metal ion present in the complexes and their ability to enter in to the bacterial cell³⁵. The solubility, conductivity and bond lengths of the complexes, influenced by the metal ions, might play a vital role in the effectiveness of the drug³⁶. The

Fig. 3. Structure of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes.

Fig. 4. Structure of Cu^{II} complex.

samples did not show any activity against Gram-negative cultures. This may be due to the unique outer membrane of the Gram-negative bacteria with low permeability³⁷, which prevents the penetration of the compounds in to their cells.

DNA binding studies :

Electronic absorption spectroscopy is an effective method to study the binding mode of DNA with metal complexes. The electronic absorption titrations were carried out by keeping the metal complex concentration constant and varying the DNA concentration. The solution after each addition of DNA was incubated for 10 min before recording the absorption spectra. Each sample solution was scanned from 200 to 800 nm. The intrinsic binding constant (K_b) was determined using Wolfe-Shimmer equation³⁸.

$$[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f) = [\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_b - \epsilon_f) + 1/K_b (\epsilon_b - \epsilon_f)$$

where, $[\text{DNA}]$ represents the concentration of DNA in base pairs, ϵ_a , ϵ_b and ϵ_f are apparent extinction

coefficient, extinction coefficient for free metal complex and extinction coefficient for the metal complex in fully bound form respectively. The K_b values were determined from the ratio of the slope to the intercept in the plots of $[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f)$ vs $[\text{DNA}]$. On increasing the concentration of CT-DNA, significant hypochromism was noticed for the ligand (Fig. 5) as well as the complexes, indicating intercalation mode of binding with DNA³⁹. For Co^{II} complex, the intensity of all the observed bands decreased in the presence of CT-DNA resulting in hypochromism with no appreciable change in the position of the bands. For Ni^{II} complex, the absorption band at 262 nm exhibited hypochromism and a bathochromic shift by 10 nm. For Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes, the absorption bands at 453 nm and 397 nm respectively exhibited hypochromism with no bathochromic shift. The K_b values for the ligand and its Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and

Fig. 5. The absorption spectra of VHQO in the presence and absence of CT-DNA.

Zn^{II} complexes were 6.629×10^5 , 1.1026×10^4 , 1.2012×10^6 , 4.071×10^5 and $7.627 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ respectively. The K_b values indicate that the DNA binding abilities follow the order : $[\text{Ni}(\text{VHQO})_2] > [\text{Zn}(\text{VHQO})_2] > \text{VHQO} > [\text{Cu}(\text{VHQO})_2] > [\text{Co}(\text{VHQO})_2]$.

DNA cleavage studies :

The extent of cleavage of super coiled pBR 322 DNA to nicked circular form has been studied using agarose gel electrophoresis. When plasmid DNA is subjected to electrophoresis, the fastest migration will be observed for the super coiled form (Form-I). If one strand is cleaved, the super coils will relax to produce a relatively slow moving open circular form (Form-II). If both strands are cleaved, a linear form (Form-III) that moves in between will be generated^{40,41}. Agarose gel electrophoresis patterns of VHQO and its metal complexes are given in Fig. 6. Lane-1 demonstrates the control experiment using DNA alone and no significant cleavage was noticed even on longer exposure of time. The ligand (Lane-2) and its metal complexes (Lane-3–6) are able to cleave the super coiled DNA (Form-I) and convert it in to open circular form (Form-II). However Form-III is not observed in any of these cases. It is concluded that the ligand and all the metal complexes efficiently cleaved the pBR 322 DNA hydrolytically, in the absence of any external reagents.

Fig. 6. Agarose gel electrophoresis patterns for the cleavage of supercoiled pBR 322 DNA by VHQO and its metal complexes. Lane-1 (DNA control), Lane-2 (DNA+VHQO), Lane-3–6 (DNA + Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes respectively).

Experimental

Materials and measurements :

All the chemicals used were of reagent grade, purchased from commercial sources and were used without any further purification. Calf-thymus (CT) DNA was purchased from Sigma. Plasmid pBR 322 DNA was obtained from SRL. IR spectra were recorded using Shimadzu FTIR-5300 spectrometer in KBr pellets from 250 to 4000 cm^{-1} . Electronic absorption spectra were recorded in DMSO in the range of 200–1200 nm at room temperature on Shimadzu UV-3600 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectrum was recorded with Bruker 400 MHz spectrometer using DMSO-*d*₆ solvent. An EPR spectrum at room temperature was obtained using Bruker Xenon EMX-ER073 spectrometer. X-Ray powder diffractograms were recorded on a SMART Bruker D8 advance X-ray diffractometer using Cu-K α λ -radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) at 40 KV and 30 mA. LCMS was recorded using Shimadzu mass spectrometer. Elemental analysis was carried out using FLASH Ea 1112 SERIES CHNS analyzer. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential thermal analysis (DTA) was carried out under nitrogen atmosphere in the temperature range of 25°C to 900°C with a heating rate of 10°C/min using TG/DTA EXTAR 6300. SEM images were recorded on MERLIN Compact SEM analyzer. Electrical conductance measurements were recorded using 10^{-3} M solutions of the complexes in DMSO with an Elico conductivity bridge and dip type cell calibrated with KCl solution. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured on a Faraday balance model 7550 at room temperature using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections were computed using Pascal's constants. DNA cleavage experiments were performed with the help of Biotech electrophoresis system supported by Genei power, visualized and photographed under BiotechTransilluminator.

Synthesis of the ligand 3-(2-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)hydrazinyl)quinoxalin-2(1H)-one (VHQO) (L) :

3-Hydrazinylquinoxalin-2(1H)-one was prepared by a reported procedure^{42,43}. The ligand (VHQO) was prepared by the condensation of 3-hydrazinyl-

quinoxalin-2(1*H*)-one with 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde. To 3-hydrazino quinoxaline-2-one (8.8 g, 50 mmol) in methanol, 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde (8.6 g, 50 mmol) in methanol was added dropwise with constant stirring at room temperature and a catalytic amount of acetic acid was added. Stirring was continued for 30 min. The yellow solid obtained was collected by filtration, washed with methanol and n-hexane and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. Yield : 89%, m.p. 224°C. Elemental analysis. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄N₄O₃ : C, 61.92; H, 4.54; N, 18.05%. Found : C, 61.81; H, 4.46; N, 17.92%. UV-Vis in DMSO λ_{max} (nm) : 266, 276, 358, 377, 397. IR (ν cm⁻¹; KBr) : 3581 ν(OH) phenolic, 1678 ν(C=O), 1614 ν(C=N)_{free}, 1465 ν(C=N)_{ring}, 1344 ν(C-O). ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆ ppm) : δ 12.43 (1H, quinoxaline ring NH), 11.66 (2H, OH and free NH), 8.7 (1H, azomethine CH), 6.8–8.8 (7H, Ar-H), 3.9 (3H, O-CH₃). LCMS(+) : *m/z* 311 [M+1]⁺.

Synthesis of metal complexes :

To a hot methanolic solution of metal(II) chloride in a two necked round bottom flask, hot methanolic suspension of VHQO (L) was added in small increments. It is observed that the ligand dissolves completely in the presence of metal ions and a clear solution was obtained after each addition. The metal to ligand ratio was maintained at 1 : 2 in all the cases. The pH of the reaction mixture was then raised to 7 using alcoholic ammonia. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for about four hours. The colored solid obtained was filtered in hot condition, washed with methanol and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride.

[Co(C₁₆H₁₃N₄O₃)₂] : m.p. >300°C. Elemental analysis. Calcd. for C₃₂H₂₆CoN₈O₆ : C, 56.72; H, 3.86; N, 16.53%. Found : C, 56.45; H, 3.78; N, 16.42%. UV-Vis in DMSO λ_{max} (nm) : 412, 459, 485. IR (ν cm⁻¹; KBr) : 1670 ν(C=O), 1600 ν(C=N)_{free}, 1436 ν(C=N)_{ring}, 1363 ν(C-O), 640 ν(M-O), 405 ν(M-N). LCMS(+) : *m/z* 677.

[Ni(C₁₆H₁₃N₄O₃)₂] : m.p. >300°C. Elemental analysis. Calcd. for C₃₂H₂₆NiN₈O₆ : C, 56.74; H, 3.86; N, 16.54%. Found : C, 56.67; H, 3.79; N,

16.48%. UV-Vis in DMSO λ_{max} (nm) : 399, 468.5. IR (ν cm⁻¹; KBr) : 1674 ν(C=O), 1602 ν(C=N)_{free}, 1438 ν(C=N)_{ring}, 1361 ν(C-O), 466 ν(M-O), 414 ν(M-N). HRMS : *m/z* 677.1401.

[Cu(C₁₆H₁₃N₄O₃)₂] : m.p. >300°C. Elemental analysis. Calcd. for C₃₂H₂₆CuN₈O₆ : C, 56.34; H, 3.84; N, 16.42%. Found : C, 56.45; H, 3.78; N, 16.32%. UV-Vis in DMSO λ_{max} (nm) : 402, 455, 482. IR (ν cm⁻¹; KBr) : 1647 ν(C=O), 1593 ν(C=N)_{free}, 1365 ν(C-O), 567 ν(M-O), 497 ν(M-N). LCMS : *m/z* 682.

[Zn(C₁₆H₁₃N₄O₃)₂] : m.p. >300°C. Elemental analysis. Calcd. for C₃₂H₂₆ZnN₈O₆ : C, 56.18; H, 3.89; N, 16.38%. Found : C, 56.38; H, 3.76; N, 16.21%. UV-Vis in DMSO λ_{max} (nm) : 432, 457. IR (ν cm⁻¹; KBr) : 1672 ν(C=O), 1606 ν(C=N)_{free}, 1444 ν(C=N)_{ring}, 1359 ν(C-O), 405 ν(M-O), 396 ν(M-N). HRMS : *m/z* 684.2078.

Antibacterial activity :

The *in vitro* antibacterial activity of VHQO and its complexes were tested against the Gram-positive bacterial species *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis* and Gram-negative bacterial species *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in nutrient agar media by antibiotic sensitivity assay. DMSO was used as negative control.

DNA binding studies :

The ability of the ligand and its metal complexes to bind to calf-thymus (CT)-DNA has been evaluated by absorption spectroscopy. Electronic absorption titrations were performed in KH₂PO₄ and K₂HPO₄ buffer using the solutions of metal complexes in DMSO solution. A solution of CT-DNA in the buffer gave a UV absorbance ratio at 260 nm and 280 nm of about 1.88 : 1, indicating that the DNA is sufficiently free from protein contamination. The concentration of CT-DNA was determined from the absorption intensity at 260 nm and ε value (6600 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹). Stock solutions were kept at 4°C and used within four days.

DNA cleavage studies :

The ability of the ligand and its metal complexes

to cleave super coiled pBR 322 DNA has been studied using agarose gel electrophoresis. pBR 322 DNA dissolved in 5 mM Tris.HCl/50 mM NaCl buffer (pH 7.2) was treated with the ligand and its metal complexes. The mixture was incubated for 2 h at 37°C. A loading buffer containing 1% bromophenol blue and 40% sucrose (1 µL) was added to the incubated solution and loaded on to a 0.8% w/v agarose gel containing ethidium bromide (1 µg/ml). Control solution using DNA alone was also loaded. The gel was run in Tris acetate EDTA (TEA) buffer (40 mM Tris base, 20 mM acetic acid, 1 mM EDTA), (pH 8.3) at constant voltage of 60 V for 2 h until the bromophenol blue had traveled through 80% of the gel. The bands were photographed under UV transilluminator.

Conclusions

The Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of tridentate Schiff base ligand, 3-(2-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)hydrazinyl)quinoxalin-2(1H)-one (VHQO) were synthesized and characterized by various spectral and analytical techniques. The ligand formed 1 : 2 complexes (ML₂) with the metal ions (M) and all the complexes were found to be monomeric with an octahedral geometry. The ligand behaved as N, N, O donor in Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes coordinating through ring nitrogen, azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen and behaved as O,N,O donor in Cu^{II} complex coordinating through carbonyl oxygen, azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen. The ligand and its metal complexes were screened for antibacterial activity and found that the ligand and its Cu^{II} complex exhibited moderate activity against *Bacillus subtilis* while the ligand and its Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes exhibited moderate activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*. The binding abilities of the ligand and its metal complexes with CT-DNA were investigated by absorption spectroscopy, which show their strong binding abilities. In the DNA cleavage studies by gel electrophoresis the ligand and its metal complexes effectively cleaved the super coiled pBR 322 DNA to nicked circular form.

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